

Explorations in Multidisciplinary Research

The Influence of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Fund Receipts, Net NPF (Non Performing Financing), Mudharabah Income on CAR (Capital Adequacy Ratio) with Firm Size as a Moderation Variable in Islamic Banking in Indonesia Period of 2018-2023

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the effect of ZISWAF fund receipts, NET NPF and mudharabah income on CAR (Capital Adequacy Ratio) with Firm Size as a moderating variable. The sample used in this research is listed in the (OJK) period 2018Q1-2023Q3. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling, with a total sample of 115 companies. The data analysis technique used is Panel Data Regression Analysis and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) with the Eviews 12 application. The research results found that the receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds had a significant negative impact on CAR in the financial sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period. Npf nett has a significant negative effect on CAR in the financial sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period. mudharabah income has a significant negative impact on CAR in the financial sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period. Firm size is able to moderate the influence of mudharabah income on the financial sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period.

Keywords: ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Net NPF, Mudharabah Income, CAR, Firm Size.

Introduction

The sharia banking system applies the principle of avoiding loans that could harm a person's relationship with God through conditions called Sharaq. The performance of sharia banks recorded significant growth, sharia credit in Indonesia increased from 0.7% to 1.2% of total bank loans. This increase is due to the increase in sharia banking in Indonesia, which currently has two full banks and several traditional branches offering sharia products. (Imam and Kpodar, 2016).

Research has been carried out on several things that could indirectly influence the growth rate of the sharia banking and finance sector. Based on this research, several indicators have been identified that cause the rate of increase in the Islamic banking and finance sector. First, the financing factor is the cause of the growth rate of the Sharia banking and finance sector. Second, the financial stability factor is another factor that influences the growth rate of the Sharia banking and financial sector. Third, regulatory factors are also factors that influence the growth rate of the sharia banking and finance sector. Fourth, work skills and abilities are another factor that influences the growth rate of the Islamic banking and finance sector (Nawaz, 2019).

Introducing sharia financial literacy in the distribution of funding from zakar, shadaqah, Waqf and Fitrah (Jislaw) among citizens is one of several steps that can be taken to strengthen understanding and use of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds

in accordance with Sharia (Sardiana and Zulfison, 2016) .

Success in promoting the quality of social financing is highly dependent on the effectiveness of zakat and waqf collection strategies. However, to ensure the success of this strategy, there are several aspects that must be considered. First, the procedure for returning zakat and waqf funds must be transparent and accurate. Second, it is important to choose the right and trusted institution as the recipient of zakat and waqf. Furthermore, it is necessary to carry out strict and regular monitoring to ensure that the use of zakat and waqf funds is in accordance with the stated needs and objectives. Apart from that, it is also important to develop a program for regularly utilizing zakat and waqf funds. Finally, technological development and transparency are needed to better monitor and manage zakat and waqf finances. By implementing effective zakat and waqf fund collection strategies, it is hoped that these funds can be optimal for a prosperous society (Aziz et al. 2021) .

In the context of sharia banking, NPF reflects the performance of a bank. This ratio describes the proportion of funds that cannot be realized by the borrower. While this is largely due to strict credit regulations in Islamic banking and increased scrutiny of bank performance, there are other things that can affect Islamic banks' profits, including increased costs and tighter controls on loan repayment. This research also highlights the importance of mapping the NPF ratio in sharia and conventional banking. as a standard for measuring bank performance, but it should be noted that other factors such as operational costs, investment performance and operational performance must also be considered when measuring bank performance (Wahyu et al. 2023) .

Analysis of Non-Performing Finance (NPF) in the broad segment and small segment in three Sharia Banks in Indonesia was carried out to gain an understanding of the relationship between NPF and the micro segment in these banks. The findings from this analysis were that NPF had negative factors on the quality of sharia banks owned by the state in Indonesia. The author also highlights that the impact of NPF on the performance of state-owned sharia banks in Indonesia may have an impact on bank operations, including in terms of identifying appropriate customers, managing high-risk loans, and providing lower-risk credit (Kuswahariani et al., 2020) .

Impact financial ratios on The benefits of Islamic banks have been tested through studies with statistical analysis. research with this secondary data sourced from a series of monthly data on sharia financial ratios issued by Bank Indonesia or (OJK) from 2006 to 2018. Which shows that (CAR) and (NPF) are significant variables, while (FDR) and (BOPO) are identified as factors main role in increasing the profits of Islamic banks in Indonesia. When using (ROA) as an indicator, NPF shows the results bad and relevant, on the other hand BOPO has no impact bad even stable. From this research, it can be found that general financial indicators can influence the increase or decrease in the financial performance of Islamic banks in Indonesia (NurJanah and Siregar, 2018) .

In the Al-Mudharabah system, investors are responsible for investment risks, while managers or administrators are responsible for operational risks. There are several important aspects related to the treatment rules for sharing the results of Al-Mudharabah financing, namely: First, implementation of Al-Mudharabah in Sharia financial institutions. Second, the profit sharing mechanism in Al-Mudharabah financing. Third, the terms and conditions that must be complied with in carrying out Al-Mudharabah. Fourth, case study and practice of using Al-Mudharabah in Sharia financial institutions (Susana and Prasetyanti, 2011) .

CAR is an indicator that measures a bank's capacity to manage risks related to loans or other productive products. The results of this research state that CAR, (BOPO), (NPF), and (FDR) have a positive impact on (ROA) Islamic banks. The positive influence of CAR shows that it is increasingly looming CAR level, makes the bank's expertise efficient when managing the risks associated with each loan or product. In addition, changes in CAR, BOPO, NPF, and FDR conditions impact the profits of our country's sharia banks, especially due to improvements in risk management capabilities and banks' ability to respond to loan requests (Li et al., 2016) .

The influence of company size, (GCG), and (CSR) on quality of work financial BUS in Indonesia has been investigated. It was found that company size has an impact relevant bad on quality of work finance (ROA) of buses in Indonesia. And it could indicate that the BUS has high scale and capital has not attracted investors' interest in improving risk management. As a result, the firm -level impact on The quality of BUS financial work in Indonesia has an impact on the profits of Islamic banks (Munir, 2018) .

Literature review

Sharia Banking

According to (Imam and Kpodar, 2016) Islamic banking is an alternative banking system to the conventional banking system. Meanwhile, according to (Wilarjo, 2014) An Islamic bank is an authority whose operations are not based on interest rates but rather a profit sharing system. Sharia Bank is a banking institution with performance procedures even the goods arranged in the Al-Quran and Hadith of the Prophet.

Ziswaf

Ziswaf is an abbreviation of Zakat, Infaq, Alms and Waqf which are combined into one form of zakat in Islamic studies (Uyun, 2015) . Broadly speaking, the word zakat appears In Arabic "zaka" means holy, growth, development, or bringing blessings (Hafidhuddin, 1998) . In Islamic terms, according to Qardhawi, zakat is defined as an amount of wealth that must be expended after reaching a certain nishab, given to appropriate servants at certain times and conditions, while adhering to the legal rules of God Almighty. (Qardhawi, 1996) .

NPF Nett

Non-Performing Financing (NPF) is a term generally used in the sharia banking industry to refer to credit or financing that has matured and the payment cannot be fulfilled by the customer or borrower. Alternatively, NPF refers to financing that fails to be repaid on time and has passed the specified payment deadline. The existence of NPF causes losses for sharia banking because the funds that have been given cannot be returned in full. Therefore, Islamic banks apply strict rules and measures to assess credit risks and reduce risks related to NPF. By carrying out intense monitoring and supervision of customers, so that they can take appropriate steps if an NPF risk occurs (Wilda, 2020) .

Al Mudharabah

Al-Mudharabah is one of the sharia principles that regulates the relationship between financiers and contractors in financing transactions (Susana and Prasetyanti, 2011) . According to Latif, CA (2020) Linguistically, the term "mudharabah" comes from the Arabic phrase "al-dharb fi al-Ardh" which literally means "service trip". The formula was chosen because in practice, regulators and managers carry out mudharabah like trading on your orders ownership of property to seek profit. In broad scope, it refers to a situation where a capital owner entrusts his capital to an amil for use in trading, with the resulting profits being shared according to the agreement stipulated in the

agreement. Therefore, mudharabah can be considered an agreement working together by who has capital and who runs capital where the distribution of profits and deficits is carried out in accordance with the agreement both of them.

CAR

Capital adequacy ratio (CAR) is a parameter about how risky the bank's assets are, including its products supported by its own capital as well as capital obtained from external sources of the company. Where CAR is bank work quality standards that assess initial money capacity the company used to support its assets risky, such as credit provided, which has the potential to affect bank profits (Dendawijaya, 2009).

Firm Size

Company size is a fundamental parameter that reflects the scale of sales and the level of internal control of the company. If it is higher, the stability rating can be said to be more supportive and involves quite a large number of stakeholders. The business decisions taken will influence people's views on the decisions they take. Therefore, they can carry out financial reporting more thoroughly and relevantly (Purwanti and Rahardjo, 2012).

Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on CAR (H1)

Receipt of Zakat or ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds does not have a direct influence on the capital adequacy ratio (CAR). This is because the CAR value is determined by the comparison between capital and assets exposed to risk. CAR is a comparison between the capital required to reduce the risk of bank losses and the value of assets exposed to risk. Although the receipt of zakat funds can influence capital requirements to reduce the risk of bank losses, it does not have a direct impact on its mobilization (Cohen, 2013).

Influence of Net NPF on CAR (H2)

The relationship between (NPF) and (CAR) reflects how a bank's financial condition, as measured by CAR, affects its ability to generate income from lending activities, as measured by NPF achievement. A higher CAR has the potential to increase the NPF because it allows banks to take more risks in providing credit, so they can earn quite large profits. Conversely, a low CAR can create a low NPF due to restrictions on the bank's ability to take risk, which can then result in lower income. (Ryad and Yuliawati, 2017).

Effect of Mudharabah Income on CAR (H3)

The relationship between mudharabah income and CAR is complex, because these two variables influence mudharabah with a positive relationship, but the relationship between them themselves is not explained in the research provided. However, it can be concluded that CAR influences mudharabah income. For example, mudharabah income can increase when CAR is excessive, because banks can receive excess funds from customers who have higher trust in the institution. This can encourage institutions to finance more mudharabah projects, which will increase mudharabah income (Munawaroh, 2023).

The Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on Firm Size (H4)

Receipt of zakat funds based on company size has a positive impact on the relationship between company size and (ROA) and operational profit for the intermediate variables. By analyzing zakat fund receipts, non-halal income, and zakat management in sharia financial institutions, you can improve risk management in zakat fund management. This success depends on the level of intelligence and innovation possessed by the

company internally (Wahyu et al., 2023) .

Influence of Net NPF on Firm Size (H5)

The influence and correlation between Net Profit After Tax (NPF Nett) and company size has a positive impact on company profitability. NPF Nett, which is the value of profit after tax, functions as an indicator to evaluate the economic performance and success of a company (Wardana et al., 2015). In the context of sharia banking, the impact of Net NPF on company size can be used as a measure of a bank's financial performance, as well as a tool to assess whether the bank's financial performance is in accordance with standards or still needs improvement. (Ilmi and Fatimah, 2020) .

Effect of Mudharabah Income on Firm Size (H6)

The impact and relationship between mudharabah income and company size can contribute positively to company profitability. Mudharabah Income, which comes from Mudharabah activities, includes Mudharabah Financing and Mudharabah Income, which is a source of income for the company. Mudharabah income serves as an indicator for evaluating the company's economic performance and success, and can also be a tool for assessing the quality of work and profitability of the organization. Increasing mudharabah income can increase citizens' confidence in business actors, which in turn can influence business performance and profitability growth (Ilmi and Fatimah, 2020) .

The Influence of Ziswaf Fund Receipts, Net NPF, and Mudharabah Income on CAR (H7)

The results of research using CAR as a tool for analyzing the quality of work of sharia banks conclude that receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Net NPF and mudharabah income have an influence on CAR. This research shows that the performance of Islamic banks exceeds conventional banks in various aspects, including CAR, LDR, NPL, BOPO, ROA, ROE, and GCG (Dachlan, 2014) .

The following is the relationship between the independent and dependent variables:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Processed by the author (2024)

Methodology

Research apply a quantitative approach. The information analyzed is statistics non-

primary from annual documents available via the OJK website starting the first quarter 2015 period to the third quarter of 2023 period.

study approach applied here involves Panel Data Regression Models and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). Engagement testing, also known as Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA), utilizes critical methods in order to maintain representative authenticity and make reference as consideration impact of moderator elements (Ghozali, 2016) .

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + e_i$$

Where:

- Y = CAR
- α = Constant
- β = Regression Coefficient
- X1 = Ziswaf Fund
- X2 = Net NPF
- X3 = Mudharabah Income
- Ei = Error

Deep hypothesis testing research the utilise regression studies with moderation components Moderating Regression Analysis (MRA), equality relationship to interaction elements with the following equation calculations

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_1*Z + \beta_5X_2*Z + \beta_6X_3*Z + \beta_7*Z + e_i$$

Where:

- Y = CAR
- α = Constant
- β = Regression Coefficient
- X1 = Ziswaf Fund
- X2 = Net NPF
- X3 = Mudharabah Income
- Z = Firm Size
- X1*Z = Multiplicative interaction between ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds and firm size
- X2*Z = Multiplicative interaction between net npf and firm size
- X3*Z = Multiplicative interaction between mudharabah income and firm size
- Ei = Error

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	X1	X2	X3	Y	Z
Mean	25082.01	2.314609	28386.30	2600.174	1665.104
Maximum	669879.0	4.980000	221513.0	14968.00	1958,000
Minimum	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	1016,000	1412,000
Std. Dev.	87500.44	1.401566	37220.81	1896.131	147.4160
Observations	115	115	115	115	115

Source: Eviews 12 (data processed by the author)

In table 1, the total number of research illustrations on the financial sector is 115 illustrations from the 2018Q1 – 2023Q3 period. For variable (X1), based on the results of descriptive statistics in Table 1, it can be concluded that the variable has an average of 25082.01, a maximum value of 669879.0, a minimum value of 0.000000, and a standard deviation of 87500.44. in the variable (X2) following the results of the descriptive statistics contained in Table 4.1, it can be obtained that the calculated variable has an average value of 2.314609, a maximum value of 4.980000, a minimum value of 0.000000, and a standard deviation of 1.401566. In the variable (X3) combined with the results of the descriptive statistics in Table 4.1, it can be seen that the variables which add up have an average value of 28386.30, a maximum value of 221513.0, a minimum value of 0.000000, and a standard deviation of 37220.81. In the variable (Z), the total descriptive statistics found in Table 4.1 show that the calculated variable has an average value of 1665.104, a maximum value of 1958.000, a minimum value of 1412.000, and a standard deviation of 147.4160. In the variable (Y), based on the descriptive statistical output in Table 4.1, it can be explained about the company value variable which in total has an average value of 2600.174, a maximum value of 14968.00, a minimum value of 1016.000, and a standard deviation of 1896.131.

Selection of Regression Model Data Panel

Test Chow

Test to find out the best pattern between the Common Effect Model (CEM) and Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Table 2. Chow Test Results

Effects Test	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	7.687125	(4,107)	0.0000
Chi-square cross-section	29.049084	4	0.0000

Source: Eviews 12 (data processed by the author)

Sticking to table 2, it was found that the probability cross-section chi-square value was $0.0000 < 0.05$. Finally, we can explain this test, the best model to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Hausman test

The Hausman test was created to determine the best method between the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and the Random Effect Model (REM).

Table 3. Hausman Test Results

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistics	Chi-Sq. df	Prob.
Random cross-section	10.418012	3	0.0153

Source: Eviews 12 (data processed by the author)

Based on table 3 above, it is found that the results of the Hausman test show a probability of $0.153 < 0.05$. Finally, it can be concluded from this test that the most important technique to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

LM Test

Table 4. LM Test Results

	Test Hypothesis		
	Cross-section	Time	Both
Breusch-Pagan	36.49473 (0.0000)	1.557946 (0.2120)	38.05267 (0.0000)

Source: Eviews 12 (data processed by the author)

Based on table 4 above, it can be found that the results of the lm test show a Breusch-pagan value of $0.0000 < 0.5$. Finally, it can be concluded from this test that the best technique to use is the Random Effect Model (REM).

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test

Table 5. Normality Test Results

Source: Eviews 12 (data processed by the author)

Based on figure 4 above, it is explained that the probability value is 0.000000, meaning the probability number is below 0.05 ($0.000000 < 0.05$). The conclusion is that the data in this research was not allocated in the usual way.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 6. Multicollinearity Test Results

	X1	X2	X3
X1	1,000000	-0.291751	0.563171
X2	-0.291751	1,000000	-0.090280
X3	0.563171	-0.090280	1,000000

Source: Eviews 12 (data processed by the author)

Based on table 6, the results of the multicollinearity test can be seen if the correlation figure between the independent variables as a whole is below 0.85. It is meaningful if the research data is not related to multicollinearity between independent variables.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 7. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Variables	Coefficien		t-Statistics	Prob.
	t	Std. Error		
X1	-0.000808	0.000779	-1.037106	0.3020
X2	-102.4661	42.98836	-2.383578	0.0189
X3	0.001599	0.002117	0.755054	0.4518

Source: Eviews 12 (data processed by the author)

Based on table 6, the results of the heteroscedasticity test can be seen regarding the number of probabilities obtained ranging above 0.05. A regression model is said to be free from heteroscedasticity when it has a total probability above 0.05. Until it can be formulated that the regression model in this research does not occur heteroscedasticity .

Panel Data Regression Analysis

The following is a panel data regression analysis using the best model, namely the Fixed Effect Model regression:

Tabel 8. Analisis Regresi Data Panel Fixed Effect Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	25436.08	8087.247	3.145209	0.0022
X1	-0.000445	0.002608	-0.170720	0.8648
X2	-792.3082	134.4004	-5.895133	0.0000
X3	0.003412	0.005920	0.576320	0.5656

Sumber: *Eviews 12* (data diolah oleh penulis)

Moderated Regression Analysis/MRA

A moderating variable is defined as a variable to strengthen or weaken the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The following are the test results from the moderation regression analysis:

Tabel 9. Analisis Regresi Moderasi

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	29441.93	7481.490	3.935303	0.0002
X1	-0.164938	0.235162	-0.701378	0.4846
X2	-8975.291	1252.394	-7.166507	0.0000
X3	-0.018270	0.083092	-0.219876	0.8264
Z	-14.93883	4.446000	-3.360062	0.0011
M1	8.56E-05	0.000121	0.705460	0.4821
M2	4.928698	0.752144	6.552863	0.0000
M3	1.06E-05	4.43E-05	0.239990	0.8108

Sumber: *Eviews 12* (data diolah oleh penulis)

Statistical Test

T test

T test, to check whether some of the dependent variables have a significant impact on the independent variables. Apart from that, it is also used to check what impact each independent variable has on the dependent variable tested at a significant level of 0.05 or with a confidence level of 95% and an error rate of 5%.

Tabel 10. Hasil Uji T

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	29441.93	7481.490	3.935303	0.0002
X1	-0.164938	0.235162	-0.701378	0.4846
X2	-8975.291	1252.394	-7.166507	0.0000
X3	-0.018270	0.083092	-0.219876	0.8264
Z	-14.93883	4.446000	-3.360062	0.0011
M1	8.56E-05	0.000121	0.705460	0.4821
M2	4.928698	0.752144	6.552863	0.0000
M3	1.06E-05	4.43E-05	0.239990	0.8108

Sumber: *Eviews 12* (data diolah oleh penulis)

Based on the t test (partial), when the author has carried out the research, the test results from the t test can be found, namely:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds has an impact on the CAR value. With a coefficient value of -0.164938 and a probability value of 0.4846, meaning it is less than a significant value of 0.5 or 5%. This fact shows that the receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds has an impact on CAR.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Net NPF has an impact on CAR. With a coefficient value of -8975.291 and a probability value of 0.0000, it means it is smaller than the significant value of 0.5 or 5%. This fact shows that NPF Nett has an influence on CAR.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Mudharabah income has an impact on CAR. With a coefficient value of -0.018270 and a probability value of 0.8264, this means it is greater than the significant value of 0.5 or 5%. These facts show that the Mudharabah Opinion has no effect

regarding the CAR.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): The impact of ziswaf fund receipts on CAR is moderated by firm size. With a coefficient value of 8.56E-05 and a probability value of 0.4821, this means it is smaller than the significant value of 0.5 or 5%. This fact shows that firm size is adept at moderating the receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds in relation to CAR.

Hypothesis 5 (H5): Net NPF has an impact on CAR moderated by firm size. With a coefficient value of 4.928698 and a probability value of 0.0000, it means it is smaller than the significant value of 0.5 or 5%. This fact shows that firm size is adept at moderating NPF Nett related to CAR.

Hypothesis 6 (H6): Mudharabah income has an impact on CAR, moderated by firm size. With a coefficient value of 1.06E-05 and a probability value of 0.8108, this means it is greater than the significant value of 0.5 or 5%. This fact shows that firm size is not able to moderate the influence of mudharabah income related to CAR

F test

The F test is used to examine whether sequentially the independent variables have a significant impact on the dependent variable. The following are the test results

Table 11. F Test Results

Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000
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Source: Eviews 12 (data processed by the author)

The F test in this research uses a significance value of 0.05 or 5% with the requirement that when the F significance value is <0.05 , the regression coefficient is appropriate to allocate. The F test results in table 10 above found a significance value of F of 0.000000, this value is smaller than the significance value of 0.05. So, conclusions can be drawn regarding institutional ownership and the order of capital which sequentially impacts the value of the company.

Coefficient of Determination Test

This test is so that you can find out how many independent variables are combined from the regression model in describing the variety of the dependent variable.

Table 12. Coefficient of Determination Results

Adjusted R-squared	0.523098
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Source: Eviews 12 (data processed by the author)

Based on table 11, the results of the panel data regression test affecting company value as the dependent variable, found an Adjusted R2 value of 0.523098. It can be obtained that 52.30% of the company value variable can be explained by institutional ownership and capital sequence. Meanwhile, others are explained by variables other than the regression model.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on CAR

Based on the tests listed in Table 10, the probability of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah,

Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds is 0.4846, which is less than the significance value of 0.5% or 5%. The test results also indicate a minus range, with a coefficient of -0.164938 and a t-statistic of -0.701378, indicating that the receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds has a negative impact on CAR. Thus, the researcher's assumption, namely H1: the influence of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on CAR, has the opportunity to be approved.

The results are in accordance with previous research by (Cohen, 2013) . Based on previous research, it can be concluded that receipt of Zakat or ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds does not have a direct impact on the capital adequacy ratio (CAR). This is because the CAR value is determined by the capital to asset ratio which is considered based on risk. CAR is a comparison between the capital required to reduce the risk of loss of a bank and the value of the assets received, which are considered in accordance with the risks involved. Although receipt of zakat funds can influence capital requirements to reduce the risk of bank losses, it does not have a direct impact on capital mobilization.

Influence of NPF Nett on CAR

Based on the test results recorded in Table 10, the NPF Nett probability value is 0.0000, indicating a value that is too little from the significance level of 0.5% or 5%. The test results also found a bad outlook, with a coefficient of -8975.291 and a t-statistic of -7.166507, indicating that Net NPF has a negative influence on CAR. Therefore, the hypothesis given by scientists, namely H2: the influence of Net NPF by CAR, can be taken.

These results are in line with previous research by (Ryad and Yuliawati, 2017) . Although research that has been conducted does not directly discuss the correlation between NPF and CAR, initial results explore the relationship between CAR, NPF, and (DPK) in the context of sharia bank credit delivery, but do not specifically focus on the relationship between NPF and CAR. However, the relationship between (NPF) and (CAR) illustrates how a bank's financial health, as measured by CAR, influences its ability to generate income from credit activities, as measured by NPF achievement. A higher CAR tends to increase NPF because a stronger financial position allows banks to take greater risks in providing loans, thereby potentially obtaining higher returns. Conversely, a low CAR can also cause a low NPF because a weak financial position limits the bank's ability to take risks in lending activities, which in turn can result in low profits.

Effect of Mudharabah Income on CAR

The test results recorded in Table 10 show that the probability value of mudharabah income is 0.8264, meaning that the value is higher than the significance level of 0.5% or 5%. However, the test results also indicate a minus direction, with a coefficient of -0.018270 and a t-statistic of -0.219876. Therefore, it shows that mudharabah income has a less significant effect on CAR. Thus, the theory proposed by researchers, namely H3: the effect of mudharabah income on CAR, can be accepted.

This is in line with (Munawaroh, 2023) . The relationship between mudharabah income and CAR is complex, because these two variables influence mudharabah with a positive relationship, but the relationship between them themselves is not explained in the research provided. However, it can be concluded that CAR influences mudharabah income.

The Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on CAR with Firm Size as Moderation

The test results listed in Table 10 show that the probability value of the interaction between receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds and company size is 0.4821, causing this value to be smaller than the significance level of 0.5% or even 5%. Apart from that, this test found a positive flow, with a coefficient of 8.56E-05 and a t-statistic of 0.705460. This shows that company size can strengthen the influence of receiving Ziswaf and CAR funds. Thus, the hypothesis proposed by researchers, namely H4: company size can moderate the influence of Ziswaf fund receipts on CAR, is accepted.

In line with research (Wahyu et al., 2023) . Receipt of zakat funds according to company scale has a positive impact on the relationship between company size and ROA and operational profit as an intervention factor. By analyzing zakat fund receipts, non-halal income, and zakat management in sharia financial institutions, it will enable you to more effectively manage risks in zakat fund management. This success depends on the knowledge and innovation possessed by the workforce concerned (Wahyu et al., 2023) .

The Influence of Net Npf on CAR with Firm Size as Moderation

Based on the test results listed in Table 10, the probability value of the interaction between Net NPF and company size is 0.0000, finding the figure lower than the significance level of 0.5% or 5%. Apart from that, the results were found to be positive, with a coefficient of 4.928698 and a t-statistic of 6.552863. This explains that company size can increase the influence between NPF Nett and CAR. Thus, the research provided by researchers, namely H5: company size is able to moderate the influence of Net NPF on CAR, is accepted.

In line with research conducted (Ilmi and Fatimah, 2020) , (Wahyu et al. 2023) . That the influence and relationship of Net Profit After Tax (NPF Nett) on company size has a positive effect on company profitability. NPF Nett, which is net profit after tax, is used as an indicator to evaluate economic performance and company achievements. In the sharia banking sector, the influence of Net NPF on a company scale can be a measure of a bank's financial performance, potentially as an indicator of whether the bank's financial performance has been running satisfactorily or still needs improvement.

The Effect of Mudharabah Income on CAR with Firm Size as Moderation

The analysis results in Table 10 show that the probability of interaction between mudharabah income and company size is 0.8108, indicating that this figure is observed to be higher than the significance level of 0.5% or 5%. Apart from that, the test results show a positive direction, with a coefficient of 1.06E-05 and a t-statistic of 0.239990. Thus, it can be found that company size has the potential to strengthen the influence between mudharabah income and CAR. Based on these findings, the hypothesis proposed by researchers, namely H6: company size can play a moderating role on the effect of mudharabah income on CAR, can be accepted.

In line with previous research by (Ilmi and Fatimah, 2020) . The impact and relationship between mudharabah income and company size can produce a positive effect on company profitability. Mudharabah income comes from one of the sources of income obtained by the center from Mudharabah activities, within the scope of Mudharabah wages and Mudharabah Income. Mudharabah income can function as an indicator for evaluating the economic performance and success of a company, as well as material for assessing the performance and profitability in question. Increasing Mudharabah income can strengthen public trust in business actors, which will

ultimately influence business performance and profitability growth.

The Influence of Ziswaf Fund Receipts, Npf Nett, and Mudharabah Income on CAR

Based on the results of the analysis in Table 11, it can be found that the variables ziswaf fund receipts, NPF Nett, and mudharabah income have a significant influence on the value of the institution. This is proven by the significance value of 0.000000, which is too low than the specified rule level, namely 0.05. These results confirm that receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, NPF Nett, and mudharabah income influence company figures. Therefore, the research allocated by the researcher, namely H7: The effect of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, NPF Nett, and mudharabah income on company value, can be used. Apart from that, R Square found a figure of 0.523098, which was found to be 52.30% explained by the variable while the rest was due to other things.

Conclusion

In the results of this test, it was found that receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds had a significant negative influence on CAR. This means that an increase in ziswaf fund receipts will cause a decrease in CAR, and vice versa. Likewise with Net NPF and mudharabah income, both of which also show a significant negative influence on CAR. Furthermore, in the interaction of the moderating variable, firm size is able to change the influence of ziswaf fund receipts on CAR in the 2018q1-2023q3 quartiles. The same thing also happens to NPF Nett and mudharabah income, where firm size can moderate the influence of both on CAR in that quartile period.

For future research, it is recommended to consider the use of different moderating variables. Apart from that, trying the annual research method can also provide different insights in understanding the differences in results between the quartile and annual methods, and can complete the understanding of the financial condition of other Sharia banks.

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